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Impact of Socioeconomic Conditions on Students' Academic Performance in District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic performance in District Dir Lower, KP. The study utilized simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were utilized for selecting sample. In four tehsils of District Dir Lower, 20 high schools were randomly selected, and 15 students were purposively chosen, resulting in a total of 300 students. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The data were analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The study found that socioeconomic conditions have a statistically significant impact on students' academic performance. This study adds to the existing literature by contributing meaningful information for parents, teachers, and policymakers on how socioeconomic conditions influence students' academic performance. The findings provide guidance for educators to recognize the significance of parental education and involvement in children's education and to strengthen school-home collaboration. They also inform policy initiatives aimed at generating employment opportunities and income support programs to assist low-income families, as well as community and population programs addressing issues related to family sizes. Moreover, the findings provide guidelines for future research aimed at improving students' academic performance.

Keywords: Parental Education, Family Income, Family Size, Parental Employment, Parental Involvement in Education, Students' academic performance

INTRODUCTION

Education is the eyes from darkness to the light and a vital instrument of social development. It expands intellectual capability, promotes the ability to distinguish between right and wrong, good and bad, and enables individuals to use their environment collectively for the wellbeing of themselves and society (Ahmad & Khan, 2012). Education is an important for societal development, as an educated society produce citizens that are more civilized and disciplined in all aspects of life (Asmatullah & Kiazai, 2022). Nations that have invested significantly in education have contributed to advancements in science and the latest knowledge, creating opportunities for new products and technology (Runde et al., 2023). Education is generally considered a crucial factor influencing socioeconomic attainments, as it offers a route to enhance opportunities and improve the quality of life (OECD, 2020). As a basis for socioeconomic empowerment, education is the basic infrastructure for obtaining jobs, and good jobs are a means of poverty alleviation. It improves health outcomes, promotes gender equality, and contributes to societal peace and stability. Education benefits both individuals and societies. At the individual level, education increases employability, income, and healthcare, and reduces poverty. For a societal level, education derives economic growth, fuels innovation, strengthens institutions, and promotes social cohesion (World Bank, 2025).

One important aspect of education in which students successfully obtain knowledge and skills is academic performance. Academic performance is a crucial indicator of a student's success and achievement within an academic institution in their educational journey. It can be measured through examination results, such as percentage score or cumulative grade point average (CGPA), test scores, and the overall engagement in the learning process. It reflects the extent to which students achieve their academic goals and is a key indicator of learning outcomes that can significantly affect future educational and career opportunities. Students with strong academic performance often achieve greater economic and occupational opportunities (Aderson, 2024; Hailu et al.,

2024).

Academic performance is affected by a range of factors, with socioeconomic conditions being one of the most significant (Al Husaini & Shukor, 2022). Socioeconomic conditions have a substantial influence on educational attainment and the learning environment of students. Children from economically advantaged households face fewer issues and have sufficient resources and opportunities to utilize their skills and talents in their educational careers (Sanaullah et al., 2022). Conversely, children from poor socioeconomic backgrounds face barriers that limit their choices and opportunities, encountering challenges in accessing educational opportunities and showcasing their skills and talents (Sanz, 2024). Children from low socioeconomic status families develop their academic abilities more slowly than children from advanced socioeconomic communities. The children from low socioeconomic status are linked with weak cognitive development, language, memory, and many other socioeconomic issues such as low income and poor health (American Psychological Association, 2017).

Families with an advanced socioeconomic position have a strong financial position and resources to devote towards their children's development, enabling them to attend quality schools, avail tuition, and participate in activities that enhance their knowledge and academic success (Zhang & Xie, 2016; Latif et al., 2022). These advantages not only facilitate academic success but also provide a supportive environment for intellectual, societal, and mental growth. Moreover, such families are possibly engage in educational activities of their children's at home, help with schoolwork, and foster a positive attitude toward education. Students from higher socioeconomic status also benefit from broader access to educational role models, cultural experiences, and strong social networks, all of which serve to enhance academic learning and outcomes (Munir, et al., 2023). Building on this understanding, the existing study investigates the impact of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic performance in District Dir Lower with the following specific objectives and hypotheses.

Objectives

To examine the impact of parental education on students' academic performance in Dir Lower

To investigate the impact of family income on students' academic performance in Dir Lower

To evaluate the influence of family size on students' academic performance in Dir Lower

To assess the effect of parental employment on students' academic performance in Dir Lower

To study the impact of parental involvement in education on students' academic performance in Dir Lower

Hypotheses

Parental education has no significant impact on students' academic performance.

Family income has no significant impact on students' academic performance.

Family size has no significant influence on students' academic performance.

Parental employment has no significant effect on students' academic performance.

Parental involvement in education has no significant impact on students' academic performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sulaiman et al. (2020) examined the effect of parental socioeconomic on the academic

attainment of undergraduate students in Malaysia. A descriptive study was designed to collect data from 333 students through a semi-structured questionnaire. The findings indicate that the majority of students claimed that their academic achievement was not affected by parental socioeconomic status. Lurie et al. (2021) also studied the mechanisms linking the socioeconomic positions and childhood academic success. The findings show that socioeconomic status is linked with language development, which in turn enhances the academic achievement. A descriptive study was conducted by Islam and Khan (2017), and data were collected from 170 students. Although academic achievement was significantly different among the various groups of socioeconomic status, the results discovered a positive link between socioeconomic status and students' academic success. Similarly, Muner et al. (2023) observed that children from higher socioeconomic status often have an inspiring home environment. They have greater and easier access to books, educational materials, and intellectual motivation, which in turn positively influence academic achievement. The knowledge, skills, and behaviors that are cultural capital communicated through socialization affect the academic success of the students. In the study of Bhat et al. (2016) in the district of Jammu and Kashmir state, data were gathered from 120 students. The findings indicate a significant difference in academic outcomes between students from elite socioeconomic classes and those from low socioeconomic positions. The results indicated a significant association between the socioeconomic conditions of parents and children's academic achievements in secondary examinations. Children with high parental socioeconomic conditions achieved better performance in the examination compared to children with low parental socioeconomic conditions. Sanaullah (2022) analyzed the study in District Dir Upper, Pakistan assessing the impact of the socioeconomic status of parents on students' schooling and learning outcomes. The findings reveal that parents' socioeconomic status affects students' education and academic performance. Most of the students enrolled in government schools come from poor family backgrounds, while most of the students enrolled in private schools come from upper-middle or high-income families. The majority of the students enrolled in government schools represent low-income families. The children of poor families tend to underperform academically due to limited access to educational facilities. They also remain absent to assist their families with farming, businesses, or household responsibilities, further hindering their academic progress.

The existing literature highlights the relationship and influences of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic outcomes. The majority of studies highlight a positive and substantial relationship between socioeconomic of people and students' academic outcomes. Students from prosperous families benefit from access to educational facilities and parental assistance, which positively and significantly contribute to their academic performance. On the other hand, students from low-income families are hindered by a lack of educational facilities and less parental support, negatively influencing their academic careers. Despite the fact that the socioeconomic conditions are crucial for students' academic performance, the existing literature is limited and focuses on particular regions, leaving out districts like Dir Lower. In some contexts, qualitative and descriptive studies are being conducted, but these studies have clearly ignored the quantitative aspects. To address this gap, this study proposes to quantitatively investigate the influences of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic performance and provide new knowledge to the existing literature that has never or rarely been explored before.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current study was designed in District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). District Dir Lower consists of seven tehsils, namely Tehsil Adenzai, Balambat, Lal Qilla, Khall, Munda, Samarbagh, and Timergara. Four tehsils — Adenzai, Balambat, Munda, and Timergara, were randomly selected from the seven tehsils. From each tehsil, 5 government high schools were randomly selected resulting in a total of 20 government high schools being selected. From each school, the top three students were purposively selected from class 6 to class 10. Thus, 15 students were selected from each school resulting in 75 students from each tehsil, making a total sample size of 300 students in all tehsils. A structured questionnaire was utilized to gather data in 2024. The data regarding students' academic performance (percentages) were collected from students with the assistance of the school administration, while data about socioeconomic conditions were collected from the parents (respondents) of the students. Data were analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics was applied to calculate the frequencies and percentages. Inferential statistics such as the multiple linear regression model was applied to measure the impact of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic performance as expressed in Equation below.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 D_1 + \beta_5 D_2 + \beta_6 D_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Y = Students' academic performance (percentage point)

X₁ = Parental education (Years of formal schooling)

X₂ = Family income (PKR in 000)

X₃ = Family size (No. of household members)

D₁ = Government employment (1= if parents are employed in govt. sector, 0= unemployed parents)

D₂ = Private employment (1= if parents are employed in private sector (private institutions, self-employed, business, farming), 0= unemployed parents)

D₃ = Parent involvement in education (1= involved in their children's education, 0= not involved)

ε = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the socioeconomic conditions, including parental education level, family income, family size, parental employment status, and parental involvement in the education. Table 1 provided the details of socioeconomic as under.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents' Socioeconomic Conditions

Socioeconomic Conditions	Frequencies (f)	Percentages (%)
Parental Education Level		
Illiterate	16	5
Primary	28	9
Matric	98	33
Intermediate	66	22
Bachelor and Above	92	31
Total	300	100
Family Income (Annual, PKR in 000)		
Up to 50	35	12
51–100	120	40
101–150	90	30

Above 150	55	18
Total	300	100
Family Size		
Up to 5	44	15
06 –10	172	57
Above 10	84	28
Total	300	100
Parental Employment Status		
Unemployed	23	8
Govt. Employment	112	37
Private Employment	165	55
Total	300	100
Parental Involvement in Education		
Not Involved	90	30
Involved	210	70
Total	300	100

Source: Field Study, 2024

Table 1 shows the respondents socioeconomic conditions of the students in the study area. According to the results, 98 parents (33%) had an education level of matric, followed by 92 parents (31%) with a bachelor's degree and above, 66 (22%) with an intermediate education, 28 (9%) with a primary education, while 16 (5%) were illiterate. In terms of family income, the majority of respondents, 120 (40%), had an annual income ranging between PKR 51 and 100 thousand. This was followed by 55 respondents (30%) with an income between PKR 101 and 150 thousand, 55 respondents (18%) with an income above PKR 150 thousand, and 35 (12%) respondents with an income up to PKR 50 thousand. In family size, the majority of respondents, 172 (57%), stated a family size between 6 and 10 persons, followed by 84 respondents (28%) with more than 10 persons, and 44 respondents (15%) with up to 5 persons. In parental employment status, the majority of parents, 165 (55%), were engaged in private employment, followed by 112 parents (37%) in government employment, while 23 parents (8%) were unemployed. Regarding parental involvement in education, the vast majority, 210 parents (70%), were involved, while 90 parents (30%) were not involved in education.

Academic performance of students

The students' academic performance is measured based on the percentage marks obtained by students during the academic year. Table 2 presents detailed information on the percentage marks of students from the selected schools.

Table 2

Distribution of Students Based on Percentage Marks Obtained During the Academic Year

Percentage marks	Frequencies (f)	Percentages (%)
70–80	95	32
80–90	165	55
Above 90	40	13
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 reveals the distribution of students based on percentage marks. The students were categorized into three groups: 70–80 percentage marks, 80–90 percentage marks,

and above 90 percentage marks. As shown in the table, the majority of students—165 (55%)—obtained between 80 to 90 percentage marks, followed by 95 students (32%) who obtained between 70 to 80 percentage marks, and 40 students (13%) who scored above 90 percentage marks.

Diagnostic Tests

Before estimating the proposed regression model, it is essential to perform diagnostic tests for normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity. The results of these diagnostic tests are presented below.

Normality Test

To test data normality, the Shapiro-Wilk test is generally used, and its results are depicted in Table 3.

Table 3
Test for Data Normality

Data Tested	Shapiro-Wilk Test	p- value
Dependent variable	0.994	0.152
Regression residuals	0.993	0.215

Table 3 presents the normality test for the dependent variable (raw data) and the regression residuals (errors). The null hypothesis for the dependent variable and regression residuals is that 'the data were not normally distributed'. The results indicate that the p-value of both the dependent variable (0.152) and regression residuals (0.215) was greater than the alpha value of 0.05, rejecting the null hypotheses. This suggests that the data for the dependent variable and regression residuals (errors) are normally distributed. Ahmad and Ahmad (2024) calculated the Shapiro-Wilk test and found similar results regarding the p-value, supporting the present results.

Multicollinearity Test

To test multicollinearity among the model's independent variables, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is mostly used, and its results are highlighted in Table 4.

Table 4
Test for Multicollinearity

Variables	(VIF)
Parental education	1.171
Govt. employment	1.024
Private employment	1.123
Family income	1.016
Family size	1.016
Parental involvement in education	1.140

According to the results in Table 3, the VIF values of all independent variables were less than 5. Consequently, it is stated that all independent variables in the model do not show multicollinearity. Ahmad and Jan (2023) found that the VIF is a commonly used test to diagnose multicollinearity among independent variables. If the VIF value for an independent variable is less than 5, it represents no issue of multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

To diagnose heteroscedasticity in the model, the Breusch-Pagan statistic is considered the most commonly used test, and its results are outlined in Table 5.

Table 5
Test for Heteroscedasticity

Test	Chi ² (1)	p- value
Breusch-Pagan Test	2.11	0.250

Table 5 reveals that the p-value of the Breusch-Pagan statistic (0.250) was greater than the alpha value (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating that the variance of residuals (errors) is constant, and we conclude that there is no problem of heteroscedasticity. This result is supported by Ahmad and Ahmad (2024), who also calculated that in the Breusch-Pagan test, and found similar results regarding the p-value, which supports the current findings of no issue of heteroscedasticity.

Impact of Socioeconomic Conditions on Students' Academic Performance

The section estimates the results of a multiple linear regression model and measures the impact of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic performance. In the model, students' academic performance is the dependent variable, while parental education level, government employment, private employment, family income, family size, and parental involvement in education are independent variables. The estimated results are highlighted in Table 3 below.

Table 6

Estimated Results of Multiple Linear Regression Model Measuring the Impact of Socioeconomic Conditions on Students' Academic Performance

Variables	Beta	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Constant	.424	.054	7.929	0.000
Parental education	.025	.003	7.740	0.000
Govt. employment	.088	.038	2.330	0.020
Private employment	.064	.009	7.453	0.000
Family income	.090	.037	2.449	0.015
Family size	-.072	.035	-2.092	0.037
Parental involvement in education	.015	.003	4.333	0.000

$R^2 = 0.408$

F-test = 42.57, p-value = 0.000

Table 3 shows that the coefficient of parental education is 0.025 with a p-value of 0.000, representing a positive and significant impact on students' academic performance. This shows that for each additional year in parental education level, students' academic performance increases by 2.5 percentage points. This result is corroborated with the evidences of Bhandari and Timsina (2024), who estimated that parental education has a significant and positive impact on school children's academic success. Similarly, Jafari (2021) found that an increase in paternal education significantly enhances the odds of children obtaining high scores in various subjects.

The coefficient of government employment is 0.088 with a p value of 0.015, presenting a positive and significant influence on students' academic performance. This indicates that, compared to unemployed parents, parents with government employment are associated with an 8.8 percentage point increase in students' academic performance. The coefficient of private employment is 0.064 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a positive and statistically significant association with students' academic performance. This suggests that, compared to unemployed parents, parents with private employment increase students' academic performance by 6.4 percentage points. These results align with the findings of Zalli and Teliti (2024), who found that the students whose parents

are working full-time show excellent performance compared to the students whose parents are unemployed.

The coefficient of family income is 0.090 with a p-value of 0.015, demonstrating a positive and significant association with students' academic performance. This signifies that for each additional PKR 1000, students' academic performance increases by 9.0 percentage points. This outcome is in line with the findings of Shah et al. (2021), who estimated a positive and statistically significant association between family income and student academic achievement measured by total marks. Likewise, the study of Siraj-Blatchford and Manni (2007) also observed a positive association between family income and students' academic performance. In the study of Davis-Kean (2005), the author found that higher-income families have access to educational materials, extracurricular activities, and a favorable environment, contributing to enhancing students' academic performance.

The coefficient of family size is -0.072 with a p-value of 0.037, demonstrating a negative and significant influence on students' academic performance. This advocates that for each additional member in family, students' academic performance decrease by 7.2 percentage points. This result is aligned to that of Jafarai (2021), who estimated that an increase in family size decreases the probability of obtaining scores in various subjects. Similarly, in the study of Bahr and Leigh (1987), they found that children from big families performed poorly in their academics compared to their counterparts.

The coefficient of parental involvement in education is 0.015 with a p-value of 0.000, signifying a positive and significant relationship with students' academic performance. This indicates that, compared to parents not involved, parents who are involved in their children's education increases students' academic performance by 1.5 percentage points. This finding is parallel to the results of Topor et al. (2010) and Asmatullah and Kiazai (2022), who found that students whose parents are involved in their education tend to achieve better grades and higher marks compared to those students whose parents are not or less involved. Correspondingly, Kantova (2024) found that parents involvement has a positive influence on students' academic achievements.

According to the table results, R^2 was 0.408, which indicates that 40.8% of the variation is explained by the independent variables included in the model. The value of the F-test was 42.57 with a p-value of 0.000, showing that the overall model is significant. Based on this discussion, we conclude that the p-value of parental education, parental employment, family income, and parental involvement is less than 0.05. Therefore, we accept that all socioeconomic conditions have a significant impact on students' academic performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Education plays an important role in societal development and individual growth; however, students' academic performance is profoundly affected by socioeconomic conditions. Factors such as parental education, employment status, involvement in education, family income, and family size play a vital role in shaping students' educational outcomes. In this regard, the current study examines the impact of socioeconomic conditions on students' academic performance in District Dir Lower. The study finds that socioeconomic conditions, such as parental education, parental employment (government and private), family income, family size, and parental involvement in education, have a statistically significant impact on students' academic performance.

This research can help people, particularly parents and teachers in District Dir Lower, in understanding how socioeconomic conditions influence students' academic performance. It can contribute knowledge for researchers examining the association between socioeconomic background and educational outcomes of students. The findings can support future research to explore the impacts of parental education, their employment status, and involvement in students' success. It can also guide scholars in understanding the influences of household income and its size on students' academic performance. Overall, the study adds meaningful insights to the understanding of socioeconomic factors shaping students' academic performance.

This research helps teachers identify the significance of parental education and involvement for students' academic outcomes. The findings help government, private, and local authorities in recognizing the indirect benefits of creating employment opportunities for parents. It guides policymakers and income support programs in assisting unemployed parents and low-income families to enhance students' education. Additionally, the study informs community organizations and population planning programs to initiate awareness campaigns on the challenges associated with larger family sizes.

Delimitations and Future Directions

This study is limited to the District of Dir Lower, which may restrict the generalizability of its findings to other areas. It primarily collected short-term data from school administrations and parents, excluding personal perspectives of students. Moreover, the study focused only on boys' higher secondary schools. For future studies, it is recommended to extend the research to a broader geographical area to enhance the generalizability of the results. Incorporating long-term data would contribute to a deeper understanding of the subject. Additionally, future research should include a comparative analysis of boys' and girls' schools and investigate the individual capabilities of students across different educational institutions.

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